

Interaction Design as a Motivator

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Abstract

Product design is often intended to change the user's behavior and attitude, especially for products that carry educational functions. Digital technology works to enrich products with more interactive experiences while placing increased emphasis on the influence of user behavior. Using products aimed at facilitating children's learning as examples, this paper will explore an approach that may employ interaction design in transforming persuasive intentions into actual products for educational and motivational purposes.

The research begins with the study of persuasive technology, educational technology, and learning motivation. Then it will seek to analyze the design strategies of ten related examples based on the framework of persuasive technology. The relevance between these persuasive strategies and the aim of enhancing learning motivations will be further examined to provide an insight into how to target learners' motivation. Then as a conclusion, this paper will propose some design principles based on human-computer interaction to transform persuasive intentions into real products that may motivate children to learn.

In addition to providing the user with more experiences and emotional attachments, interaction design can influence users even more persuasively. The study proposes an approach to enhance the persuasive power of products via interaction design for the purpose of motivating children's learning. The approach may provide designers with a new tool as they proceed to design related products for children. It'll further suggest a new thinking in both industrial and interaction designs.

Keywords: Interaction design, Electronic learning toy, Motivation, Persuasive technology

Introduction

The application of digital technology brings out new possibilities for educational toys. In recent years, various electronic learning toys have grown remarkably in number and become an important industry in the market. In addition to integrating educational function with entertainment, electronic learning toys can engage kids in playing with these toys and full their educational goals with a more active interaction design. According to the constructivism theories, electronic learning toys can be effective tools for learners to build up knowledge along the learning process. To design successful learning toys, one must target the learner's motivation. Designers should understand how effective human-computer interactions are created and incorporated into some learning toys emerging in the market.

The pervasive functions of computing technology provide various human-computer interactions to establish a closer relationship with users. We have grown accustomed to

interacting with the applications of computer technology and have accepted them as a part of our lives. In addition to providing the user with more experiences and emotional attachments, these applications create interactions between human and computer to influence users even more persuasively. In commenting the ever-different role of computer technology, Dr. Fogg proposes the term “persuasive technology” to describe the fifth wave of computer technology. Persuasive technology is a new concept for designers to create influential human-computer interactions aimed at changing the user’s behavior and attitude. It has recently become a significant issue in interaction design and has been used in various domains of human life. With regard to the design of electronic learning toys, the concept of persuasive technology can provide designers with a useful means to create toys for optimal learning.

As electronic learning toys are growing into a significant industry, this paper aims to study how persuasive technologies can be integrated into toys to motivate kids to learn more effectively. The study will analyze persuasive strategies applied to electronic learning toys and further inspect the relevance between these strategies and the resulted products in providing learning motivation. The paper seeks to provide an insight into how persuasive technologies can be used to attain educational goals. The approach may provide designers with a new perspective as they proceed to design related products for children and may further suggest a new thinking in both industrial and interaction designs.

Literature review

Persuasive technology

Persuasion can be described as an active attempt to change people’s behavior and attitude. Nowadays, the widespread uses of computers and diverse computer applications have been woven into the fabric of our world. As people come into closer contact with these applications, the latter become more influential in creating interactive experiences. Fogg indicates that the fifth wave of computer technology is dominated by persuasive technology and that a successful human-computer interaction requires the skills to motivate and persuade the user [F0 and Nass 1997, Fogg 1998]. Persuasive technology reveals the area where the applications of computing technology and intentions of persuasion. Fogg stated it “focus on the design, research, and analysis of interactive computing products created for the purpose of changing people’s attitudes or behaviors” [Fogg 2002].

The study and empirical research of Persuasive Technology Lab, directed by Dr. Fogg, have gained attention in the field of HCI. The research proposed a functional trial as a framework for thinking the roles that computing products can play to attain the goal of persuading users. The functional trial can help designers to clarify how to use different persuasive strategies for changing behaviors or attitudes. The framework briefly describe as follow: 1. computers as persuasive tools can influence people by increasing their ability or making something easier to do; 2. computers as persuasive media can affect people by simulated experiences; 3. computers as persuasive social actors can influence people by creating social relationship between people and digital products.

Many studies probing into persuasive technology have emerged in recent years, such as exploring the design of environments and technologies that would motivate behavioral change [Intille *et al.* 2003], using software products to create seduction experiences [Khaslavsky and Shedroff 1999], and developing effective programs for employee training. Persuasive technology can be used in various domains in life, such as in business, education, and healthcare [Strommen 1998, Strommen and Alexander 1999]. While electronic learning toys becoming a significant trend the toy industry, the use of persuasive technology can be extended to the field of toy design to better motivate kids to learn.

Educational technology and learning motivations

Learning can be categorized into two main approaches: the acquisition model and the participatory model. In the acquisition model, learning is defined as an act of acquiring certain knowledge, more specifically, knowledge about something rather than about the thing itself. [Sfard 1998] The participatory approach, which often referred as constructivism, views learning as a process in which the learner constructs knowledge through the interaction with a tutor. Based on the two learning approaches, educational technology contains four categories : 1, Computer as a tutor: children take in information and are then quizzed; 2, Computer as a tool: Learning is an active process of constructing knowledge through experiences; 3, Computer as a tutee: The learner uses construction kits to help reinforce what he or she has learned from the process of creation; 4, Computer-supported collaborative learning: Children use the Internet to learn from and communicate with knowledgeable members of the adult community [Bandlow and Bruckman 2002].

According to constructivist theories that view knowledge as a constructed entity made by each learner through a learning process, electronic learning toys provide an optimal solution for kids to explore and discover new knowledge. These toys incorporate educational functions into games and activities to engage kids in the interactive processes and to build up their knowledge or skills more effectively. To serve their educational functions, electronic learning toys must be designed in such a way that they entice the user to learn. The following list explores the different aspects about how digital games can motivate the user to learn based on related literature review. [Keller 1992, Keller, JM, and Keller, BH 1991, Lepper and Malone 1987]

- a. Attention : One way to motivate the player to learn is to attract their attention and help them stay focused using such features as sensory stimuli, inquiry arousal, and variability.
- b. Control: The second factor depends on the degree the player can control the product.
- c. Confidence: The factor comes with the expectation to succeed, positive feedbacks, or the opportunities to attain the goal.
- d. Competition : Competition is one of the interpersonal factors that produce incentives. People appear to be driven by the tendency of comparing their own performances with that of others.
- e. Cooperation : Cooperation is another interpersonal factors that help generate sense of satisfaction through making contributions to the success of others.

Analysis of persuasive strategies employed in electronic learning toys

To understand the uses of persuasive technology as a means to achieve educational goals, we can review related designs of some award-winning pieces or toys recommended by experts. We may select 10 products as examples: (A)Power Touch Learning by Fisher Price, (B) Leadpad by Leadfrog, (C) Interactive map by GeoSafari, (D)MathSafari by Geosafari, (E)Kasey by Fisher price, (F)Robert learning pal by Vtech, (G)Musini Preschool by Neurosmith, (H)Turbo Twist of Leapfrog, (I)mathshark of Educational insights, and (J)Talking Globe by GeoSafari. The analyses are based on the functional triad that Fogg proposed to show that interactive technologies can be operated in three ways: as tools, as

media, and as social actors. Based on the framework, table 1 illustrates the different persuasive strategies employed in the design of electronic learning toys.

Examples		Persuasive strategies
A	 Power touch learning	As tools: The finger-touch pad encourages kids to follow along their fingers as they read a story. As media: Kids understand the power of reading as the story is read aloud to them to help them learn words, phonics and spelling.
B	 LeapPad	As media: It's a talking book which provides kids an interactive pen to hit the musical instruments and hear it play.
C	 Interactive map	As tools: The interactive map offers kids a way to travel through natural wonders with the touch pen. Fast-paced games designed for one or two players. As Social actors: The toy serves an opponent for the kid to compete with it.
D	 MathSafari	As tools: The sequential model and random model allow kids to learn step-by-step or to enjoy the fun provided by the challenging quizzes. As social actors: It serves as a virtual opponent by providing quizzes.
E	 Kasey	As tools: It provides step-by-step learning in many areas. As media: Problem-solving simulation. As social actors: It's a robotic toy able to move and chat.
F	 Robert learning pal	As media: It provides kids ten educational activities. As Social actors: It is a learning pal featuring character voice, sound effects and expressive eye animations on LCD screen.
G	 Musini	As tools: It can sense every vibration and respond with music to encourage kids to develop a unique relationship with music and creative movements.
H	 Turbo Twist	As Social actors: It serves as an opponent competing with a kid. It provides positive feedback as kids answer the questions.
I	 Mathshark	As tools: Its random and sequential quizzes can help kids build up mathematical skills. As Social actors: It provides instant feedback.
J	 Talking Globe	As tools: It's an interactive talking globe inviting kids to test their geographic knowledge with 11,000 questions. As social actors: It's an interactive talking globe. The "HELP" button provides clues for the player.

Table 1, Different persuasive strategies employed in the design of electronic learning toys

From Table 1 illustrates that interaction design can work as a tool, a medium, and a social actor to engage kids in playing with these toys. We may conclude that there are eight persuasive strategies integrated into electronic learning toys. The 8 strategies are listed below and illustrated as table 2 based on functional trails.

1. Interaction Design as a Tool

a. Simplified operation:

The strategy makes operation simpler to provide kids an easier way to interact with toys, such as example A and C that provide a direct and intuitive interface for manipulation.

b. Tunneling:

The strategy provides a predetermined sequence of skills or materials to lead kids to engage in learning step by step, such as example D, E, F, and I that create different guided activities.

c. Conditioning:

The strategy uses an operant conditioning for specific target behavior, such as example G that provides reinforcement through music to encourage kids to develop a unique relationship with music and creative movements.

2. Interaction Design as a Medium

a. Problem-solving simulation:

Problem-solving simulation can entice kids to solve or handle different problems or situations, such as example E and F that enable kids to explore problem-solving scenarios.

b. Object simulation:

Object simulation provides kids a rich learning experience through sounds and visuals, such as example B and E that enhance kids' sensorial experiences with voices, sounds of instruments, and animations.

3. Interaction Design as a Social actor

a. Physical cue:

Electronic learning toys can convey social presence through eyes, movements, and other physical attributes, such as example E and F that are intended to build a closer

relationship with the kids by serving as a friend.

b. Social dynamics:

Electronic learning toys can apply social dynamics to the building of a relationship with kids, such as example F, H, I, and J that are intended to induce better interaction by offering praises and assistances.

c. Social roles:

Electronic learning toys can play various roles in different situations. Example C, D, H, I, and J serve as virtual opponents in a competitive relationship with kids that are playing the games. Example D, E, F, and I are virtual tutors intended to engage kids in learning.

Interaction design as a Tool	Simplified operation	A, C
	Tunneling	D, E, F, I
	Conditioning	G
Interaction design as a medium	Problem-solving simulation:	E, F
	Object simulation:	B, E
Interaction design as a Social Actor	Physical cue	E, F
	Social dynamics	F, H, I, J
	Social roles	C, D, E, F, H, I, J

Table 2, Persuasive strategies employed in electronic learning toys

Relevance between persuasive strategies and learning motivations

Based on the conclusions above, the analyses propose eight design strategies used by educational toys to persuade kids to interact with toys. The paper will further inspect the relationship between these persuasive strategies and the users' learning motivations to provide an insight into how these means can be applied to motivate learners more effectively. Take A to J as samples. Table 3 shows the relevance between learning motivations and persuasive strategies.

	attention	control	confidence	competition	cooperation
Simplified operation	A,C	A, C	A, C		
Tunneling	E, F	D, E, F,			
Conditioning	H		H		
Problem-solving simulation	B, F				
Object simulation:	B, E	B, E			
Physical cue	E, F	E, F	E, F		E, F
Social dynamics	F,H,I,	F, J	F, H, I, J		J
Social roles	C,D,E,F,H,I,J	C, D, E, F,J		C, D, H, I, J	E, F

Table 3, The relevance between persuasive strategies and learning motivations

Table 3 reveals that these educational toys employ persuasive strategies to provide effective means to enhance intrinsic motivations in such aspects as attention, control, and confidence. Moreover, some strategies that serve as social actors can target interpersonal motivations by making cooperative relationship and competing relationship between the player and the electronic learning toy. We may further inspect how these strategies can motivate players' learning motivations.

- a. Simplified operation provides an easier way for the player to manipulate the objects. The design can encourage the player to interact with toys by ways of attracting attention, enhancing control, and building confidence, such as the finger-touch pad of example A.
- b. Tunneling interaction can serve as a step-by-step learning guide by helping the player remain focused and by providing enriched control, such as example F that features ten educational activities for kids to play with.
- c. Conditioning provides reinforcement tools to reshape the player's behavior or attitude by calling attention and building confidence, such as example G mentioned above.
- d. Problem-solving simulation can catch the player's attention by providing different scenarios. Example E enables kids to explore problem-solving scenarios.
- e. Object simulation can catch the player's attention and enrich the enjoyment of taking control via such media as sounds and visual aids. Example E responds to the player with

- simulations of sounds and animations.
- f. Physical cue conveys social presence via the product's physical features to target the player's intrinsic motivations and build a cooperative relationship between the player and the product. Example E features chatting function and the look of a robot and can act as the player's learning pal.
 - g. Social dynamics can establish a reciprocal, quasi-human relationship between the kid and the product to enhance the kid's intrinsic and interpersonal motivations. Example J provides clues for the player at his or her request and gives positive feedbacks for every correctly answered question.
 - h. Electronic learning toys can play different roles in various interactive ways to stimulate player's intrinsic and interpersonal motivations. Example I can be a virtual opponent that competes with the player in different games.

The analyses reveal that each of the aforementioned persuasive strategy can work in its own ways to entice children to learn, and that these strategies are not incompatible with one another. Designers should seek to incorporate one or more strategies in the same design to enhance the effectiveness of the product. Computer technology can be used to upgrade product functions, enrich learning experiences, establish conducive relationship between a product and its user, and thereby enhance the educational function of the product by effectively motivate the children to learn.

Conclusion

As the application of computing technology matures, it opens up new possibilities for educational products. According to constructivist theories that view knowledge as constructed by each learner through a learning process, electronic learning toys can be used as an ideal tool to invite kids to participate in the learning process. To make a successful electronic learning toy, designers may view the eight strategies discussed in this paper as design guides and seek to create an appropriate interactive experience to entice the user to learn. In addition to the eight persuasive strategies, this paper also examines the connections between these strategies and the effectiveness of the resulted products in enhancing learning motivation. This paper further provides an insight into how these strategies can be used in a more powerful way and goes on to propose a practical approach for the design of educational products aimed at enhancing kids' learning motivation. The study suggests a new thinking in

the design of educational and interactive products.

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